

Adaptive Evolution of IS Architecture in Complex Ecosystems

Rodreck David
Victoria University of Wellington
rodreck.david@vuw.ac.nz

¹Prof. Benoit Aubert (Supervisor)
²Dr Jean-Gregoire Bernard (Supervisor)

ABSTRACT

The architecture of information systems in complex organisations is increasingly becoming platform-based, creating ecosystems of platforms in which several contributors exist to benefit and complement. As such systems become complex, it is necessary to think about the evolutionary dynamics necessary to ensure continued survival and success of the architecture that holds them in place. Of specific interest are three perspectives to IS architecture, its design, governance and context. The premise of this paper is that adaptive evolution of information systems (IS) architecture in complex ecosystems has the necessary attributes to cope with evolutionary dynamics existing in its design, governance and context. The paper presents a theoretical perspective on how the rapidly changing, complex, uncertain and disruptive ecosystem environment in which IS architectural ecosystems are increasingly existing can adaptively evolve. It contributes to theoretical thinking about adaptive evolution in increasingly unstable, volatile and complex IS ecosystems. As it centres on IS architecture, the paper is directly addresses the IS artefact often skirted treated as a black box.

Keywords: *Information systems (IS) architecture; Adaptive evolution; Complex ecosystems*

INTRODUCTION

Information systems (IS) architecture in organisations have increasingly become complex, dynamic and unpredictable in their evolutionary dynamics, especially as they develop into platform ecosystems, grow, merge, unmerge and compete (Tiwana, et al. 2010; Monteiro et al., 2013; Gawer, 2014). IS architecture refers to the structural design or organisation of IS artefacts (data, information, software, hardware, networks etc.) within defined ecosystems (and their supporting and peripheral environments) aimed at enabling the usability of information products and services. Platform ecosystems can be described as dynamic and malleable IS architecture environments in which software, hardware, networks and people bound by a shared interest and common standards, contribute to the evolutionary dynamics of the ecosystem. In this paper, the focus is on the information and software environment aspect of IS architecture. Such an environment is often referred to as an extensible core which has the hub functionality upon which other modules that interoperate are connected and interface. (Tiwana et al. 2010, pp.675). Common examples today include Apple’s iOS with its tens of thousands of “apps” or Google’s browser with its numerous “add-ons.”

The trend towards extensible IS platform environments has extended to many complex organisational settings that have seen the obvious benefits such as competitive complementation, shifting value from volume, products and services to interactions, expanding the innovation capabilities, ecosystems, and greater market outreach. Consider marketplaces such as Ebay, Amazon, AliExpress; Accounting platforms such as Xero; Health portals such as WebMD, Medscape; and social media such as LinkedIn, Facebook, WeChat. In

a complex enterprise, as the combination of platforms and stand-alone systems interact within complex organisational settings, the evolutionary dynamics of IS architecture become unpredictable, with possible mutation and modification in either positive or negative direction (Tiwana, 2013 pp.93). Such circumstances create significant challenges and opportunities for both IS architecture and IS research (see Table 1). As the structure of IS architecture increasingly enter into a complex, uncertain and disruptive dynamics, its design, governance and ecosystem context requires a strategy to ensure resilience, adaptation, survival and success, in short what this paper calls *adaptive evolution*.

Table 1. Opportunities/challenges for ISA research

Opportunities/Challenges	
IS Architecture	Competition is increasingly shifting toward platform-centric ecosystems
	Conventional notion of firm boundaries is expanding
	The technical, design features and principles for structuring ISA now have a huge impact on direction of platform ecosystem survival
	Current research in platform ecosystems has tended to focus on the dynamics of their evolution not necessarily the qualities enabling their survival in an increasingly uncertain, complex and volatile environment
	Organisational systems are becoming complex as new relationships with contributors continue to grow requiring shrewd governance
IS Research	IS research is only starting to create new literature on IS architecture in platform ecosystems as the bulk of literature that exists focuses on organisations with clear boundaries
	Research on ISA uniquely provides the opportunity to address the IS artefact (Orlikowski and Iacono 2001; Benbasat and Zmud, 2003; Tiwana et al. 2010)
	Opportunity to use theoretical lenses form other disciplines, and contribute to these theories with research and theoretical reasoning from IS

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This paper proposes and advances the idea that the trajectory of development taken by IS architecture in complex ecosystems is influenced by its design, governance and context. It further proposes that *adaptive evolution* is required for ISA to survive the surrounding uncertainty, disruption, volatility and complexity. Four main research questions are developed from this proposition (See Figure 1). First, how does the design of IS architecture and its associated modules affect and influence its adaptive evolution in a dynamic and evolving complex ecosystem? (RQ1) Answering this will require an understanding of *how* and *why* successful ISA that support complex ecosystems have survived successfully. Second, how does platform governance influences adaptive evolution of ISA and its associated modules in complex ecosystems? (RQ 2) Answering this question will require an understanding of how and why platform governance can instil the necessary attributes in ISA than can enable its successful survival. Third and fourth questions (RQ 3 and RQ4) pertain to how evolutionary dynamics in contextual factors influence the adaptive evolution of ISA in complex ecosystems? Answering this question will require an understanding of the coevolutionary dynamics existing between ISA ecosystems and their contexts as well as the fit between the internal traits of an architectural design, its governance and the evolutionary dynamics of its external context (See Figure 1; Tiwana et al. 2010, pp.681). In this paper, the design aspect of IS architecture is discussed although the full study also incorporates the governance and contextual factors (See Figure 1).

RESEARCH GAP AND CONTRIBUTION TO THEORY

IS architectural survival and success referred to in this paper defines the ability of an architecture to continuously provide services to an ecosystem at the optimal level (measured by its growth diversity, complementation and innovation absorption) despite dynamic changes in its form and context over time. As IS underpins some of the most successful business models, from Amazon, Uber to Google, it is important to understand the requirements for the continuous survival and success of IS architecture, especially as it evolves to support complex platform ecosystems.

Recently, there has been an interest in exploring the evolutionary dynamics of software platform-based ecosystems which view the dynamics as influenced by the coevolution of internal governance mechanisms, and external environmental factors (Tiwana et al. 2010; 2013; 2015). This literature is interesting in that it creates questions on how complex IT systems (and therefore IT systems architecture) evolve and points to several endogenous and exogenous dynamics affecting that evolution. It however, does not go a step further, to seek to explain how and why the IS architectural environment supporting such dynamics survive and become successful or die. Why some IS architectural systems are resilient, adapt quickly even as multiple interfaces, mutations and intertwined relationships within the contextual environment emerge. These questions form the basis of this research.

IS Architecture Design

IS architecture refers to the structural design or organisation of IS artefacts (data, information, software, hardware, networks etc.) within defined ecosystems (and their supporting and peripheral environments) aimed at enabling the usability of information products and services. Platform ecosystems can be described as dynamic and malleable ISA environments in which data, information, software, hardware, networks and people bound by a shared interest and common standards, contribute to the evolutionary dynamics of the ecosystem. It is the design rules, principles and standards of the organisation of IS artefacts within IS architecture that interests this study as this influences its adaptation to evolutionary change as new variations and mutations in its form emerge. This includes the ability to interface with a growing number of modules that complementing the parent architecture, and the metamorphosis of the parent architecture itself. The interesting research question surrounding this is how the design of IS architecture and its associated modules affect and influence its adaptive evolution in a dynamic and evolving complex ecosystem.

At the design stage, the designers of IS architecture, anticipating complementarity as the architecture grows to support platforms and other complex ecosystems, need to instil attributes that support such evolutionary dynamics. They need to anticipate and accommodate changes that are unforeseen in an uncertain and complex environment to ensure that the architecture will continue to survive, thrive and successfully support the systems dependent on its services. An ideal architecture should support malleability, variety, mutation and absorption of new properties and therefore mutation whilst enabling evolvability over time (Baldwin and Woodard 2009; Tiwana et al 2010). Such traits have previously been studied in information systems in complex environments and exhibit an analogous relationship with the biological evolutionary theory of adaptive evolution. From IS research, modular system theory provides rich literature on modularisation, decomposition in the design principles and rules of IS architecture. From the biological evolutionary theory are the concepts of variance, mutation and positive selection.

Modular Systems Theory

Modular systems theory generally describes the extent to which a system's components can be disconnected and re-connected, the tightness of those connections, as well as the extent to which the 'rules' binding the system architecture enable (or prohibit) the mixing and matching of components (Schilling 2000, p.312). The theory has been at the centre of complexity and

systems research as far back as “The Architecture of Complexity” paper by Simon (1962). Simon (1962, p.468) defined modularity as an inherent characteristic of complexity which he defined as one made up of, “... a large number of parts that interact in a non-simple way.” Embedded in it are principles of *modularity* and *decomposition* which have long been considered critical in the design of complex systems (Simon, 1962; Baldwin and Clark, 2003; 2006).

a. modularity

On one hand, modularity refers to the degree to which the components that make up a system can be separated and recombined without affecting the functions of other components or creating a “ripple effect” (Schilling, 2000; Tiwana et al. 2010). This means that modules are *encapsulated* and have a degree of autonomy that allows internal processes to be independent of other complementing modules whilst subordinate to the main system and interoperating with other modules. Because they need interfaces for connections, modular systems are heavily dependent on interoperability and integration standard (Langlois, 2002, p.19). Increasing modularity in systems is has been known to enable the *flexibility* to incorporate complementary sub-systems (Sanchez and Mahoney, 1996), architectural support of specialisations (Shilling, 2000; Baldwin and Clark, 2006) enabling incremental and disruptive innovation absorption and multiple entry points for new ideas (Langlois, 2002, p. 301; Vähätalo and Kallio, 2015). It is however, the level, and extent of modularity that is critical in enabling IS architecture to survive complexity. As systems become increasingly modular, they become easy to imitate and control over a multiplicity of modules becomes inevitably impossible, sometimes leading to collapse or usurpation by rival competitors. As such the level and extent of modularity within IS architecture is viewed as a critical attribute for survival within the evolutionary dynamics of a complex ecosystem.

Figure 1. Proposed theoretical framework for adaptive evolution of IS (Platform) Architecture in Complex Ecosystems

b. decomposability

On the other hand, decomposability refers to how the organisation of a whole system if made up of and can be broken down into singular complementary atomic subsystems (Simon 1962; Tiwana et al., 2010). They are an emergent product of interconnected plugins that work autonomously and interdependently through interfaces and integration modules (Figure 1). Because they need interfaces for connections, decomposable systems are heavily dependent on rules of interoperability and integration standards. These rules define which subsystems and functionality are part of the parent IS architecture and which ones are complementary as well as the extent to which such complementarity can be provided (system boundary). Decomposition is an important attribute to IS architecture because it minimises the extent of dependence in the evolutionary dynamics of its components supporting modification, variation and mutation as well as coping with complexity as the architecture grows to support new functions in the supported ecosystem (Tiwana et al. 2010). As such, decomposition is viewed as a necessary trait that IS architecture need to possess to successfully survive a dynamic, uncertain and complex ecosystem.

c. design principles and rules

The above discussion shows that the design of IS architecture needs to abide by rules, principles and standards that enable the desired features. Attaining design features that enable an architecture to support complementation, survive changes, uncertainty, competition and complexity in a dynamic ecosystem is challenging. Design rules need to be stable enough to enable long term survival, ensuring complementors that they can make the same assumptions about other parts of the ecosystem without needing to verify those assumptions (Baldwin and Clark 2003; 2006; Tiwana et al., 2010). However, stability can be an anathema to versatility especially as some modules merge, mutate and evolve. Properties of design rules therefore need to achieve both stability and versatility to encourage variety, flexibility and adaptation to the evolutionary dynamics in a complex ecosystem. This “goldilocks zone” problem creates an interesting research question on what attributes within design rules, principles and standards are required for IS architecture to support, adapt and successfully survive.

Adaptive Evolution

Adaptive evolution refers to evolutionary changes that are fit or suited to a given environment. It comes from the general Darwinian evolution theory which explains the mechanism by which species survive (Darwin, 1859). Biologists often refer to this as the propagation of advantageous mutations of human genomes through positive selection (Klopfstein et al., 2006). Researchers have recognized the value of using evolutionary theory to as an analogy to guide their work in non-biological disciplines (Goetz & Shackelford, 2006), with the theory being used to describe many organizational changes (Burke, 2010; Tenant, 2014). An analogy can be drawn by looking at adaptive evolution in the context of IS architecture supporting complex and dynamic ecosystems. Changes proposed in adaptive evolution increase successful survivorship and adaptation as well as flexibility to endure evolutionary dynamics such as mutation, variation and competition. Inherently, adaptive evolution is affected by fitness of the internal structure of the genome and environmental factors (Hawks, 2007). Strikingly, adaptive evolution appears to have some of the prerequisite attributes of successful survivorship that evolving systems require to adapt to their changing internal and external ecosystems. These include resilience, survival, fitness, customisability, and advantageous mutation. Considering this, it is necessary to explore i) the design structure of IS architecture in complex environments, its control or governance mechanism (Tiwana et al., 2013; Wareham et al., 2014) as well as its contextual or environmental settings. This will provide an understanding as well as an explanation of how and why architectural systems evolve adaptively and therefore know why some systems are successful whilst providing explanation for those that fail.

Conclusion

This research will provide a unique insight on the adaptive evolution of IS architecture in complex ecosystems. It will provide a perspective of the design, governance and context dynamics and attributes necessary for the successful survival of IS architecture in an uncertain, ever-changing and complex ecosystem. At this conceptual stage, theoretical reasoning and a comprehensive literature review is being carried out to understand the desirable characteristics of these factors, utilising relevant theoretical lenses engaged.

References

- Baldwin, C. Y., & Clark, K. B. (2006). Modularity in the design of complex engineering systems. In D. Braha, A. A. Minai, & Y. Bar-Yam (Eds.), *Complex Engineered Systems* (pp. 175–205). Springer.
- Baldwin, C., & Clark, K. (2003). Managing in an age of modularity. Managing in the modular age: Architectures, networks, and organizations. *Harvard Business Review*, (149), 84–93.
- Benbasat, I., & Zmud, R. W. (2003). The identity crisis within the IS discipline: Defining and communicating the discipline's core properties. *MIS quarterly*, 183-194.
- Darwin, C. 1859. *On the origin of species by means of natural selection, or the preservation of favoured races in the struggle for life*. London: John Murray.
- Gawer, A. (2014). Bridging differing perspectives on technological platforms: Toward an integrative framework. *Research Policy*, 43(7), 1239-1249.
- Hawks, J., Wang, E.T., Cochran, G.M., Harpending, H.C., and Moyzsis, R.K. (2007). Recent acceleration of human adaptive evolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science Conference, USA*, 104 pp. 20753–20758.
- Klopfstein, S., Currat, M., and Excoffier, L. (2006). The fate of mutations surfing on the wave of a range expansion. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 23 pp. 482-490.
- Langlois, R. N. (2002). Modularity in technology and organization. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 49(1), 19–37.
- Monteiro, E., Pollock, N., Hanseth, O., & Williams, R. (2013). *From artefacts to infrastructures*. Computer supported cooperative work (CSCW), 1-33.
- Sanchez, R., & Mahoney, J. T. (1996). Modularity, Flexibility, and Knowledge Management in Product and Organization Design. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17, 63–76.
- Schilling, M. A. (2000). Toward a General Modular Systems Theory and Its Application to Interfirm Product Modularity. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(2), 312–334.
- Simon, H. A. (1962). The sciences of the artificial. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 106(6), 467–482.
- Tenant, V. 2014. *Understanding changes in post-adoption use of information systems (IS): A generalised Darwinism perspective*. PhD Thesis (Accounting and Information Systems). Dunedin: University of Canterbury, New Zealand.
- Tiwana, A. (2013). *Platform ecosystems: aligning architecture, governance, and strategy*. Washington D.C. Elsevier Inc.
- Tiwana, A. (2015). Evolutionary competition in platform ecosystems. *Information Systems Research*, 26(2), 266-281.
- Tiwana, A., Konsynski, B., & Bush, A. A. (2010). Research commentary-platform evolution: Coevolution of platform architecture, governance, and environmental dynamics. *Information Systems Research*, 21(4), 675-687.
- Tiwana, A., Konsynski, B., & Venkatraman, N. (2013). Special issue: information technology and organizational governance: The IT governance cube. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 30(3), 7-12.
- Vähätalo, M., & Kallio, T. J. (2015). Organising health services through modularity. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 35(6), 925–945.
- Wareham, J., Fox, P. B., & Cano Giner, J. L. (2014). Technology ecosystem governance. *Organization Science*, 25(4), 1195-1215.